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Assessment on the Competency of Nurses: Basis for a Development Program

*A Thesis Submitted to the Faculty of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies in
partial Fulfillment for the Degree Master of Arts in Nursing*

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Abstract

Casareno, Maryann G. December, 2023, Assessment on the competencies of Nurses: Basis for a Proposed Development Program, Urdaneta City University

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This study determined the competencies of nurses in public and private hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. It tackled their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, employment status and type of hospital facility. The study utilized the descriptive research design and utilized a survey questionnaire as the main tool in gathering data. Several statistical tools were used like frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance).

The nurse respondents were young adults, not into marital relationships, Bachelor's degree holder, been in the service for a few years, with regular status and mostly working in public hospitals. The nurse respondents were most competent in the areas on collaboration and teamwork, legal responsibility, management of resources and environment and personal and professional development.

Nurses who have served for 11 years and above have higher level of competency as compared to those who are 1-3 years in the service. Nurses with regular and contractual status have considered themselves more competent than the nurses who work under job order. The higher the level of educational attainment, number of years in service, and employment status of the nurse, the more competent they are in performing every aspect of their work as nurses. The proposed development program is proposed to improve the competencies of nurses.

Keywords: competencies, nurses, assessment

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Chapter 1 Introduction

Background of the Study

Nurses nowadays must be equipped with the different competencies as required to nurses in their nursing practice. Their competencies are important for a quality care to their clients especially during the pandemic time wherein surge of patients go to hospitals for medical treatment. This are challenges to nurses who were faced with burden with their work

Core competency is vital to the nursing profession. It helps guarantee the high quality, and effective delivery of care, and maintains the social value, and status of the nursing profession. The core competency profile for the nursing profession embraces basic behavioral attributes as well as mastery of advanced practice skills. The former include such attributes as gentleness, willingness to serve, keen observation and judgment, efficiency, skillfulness, responsibility and accountability. The latter embraces skills in general care, communication and collaboration, management, self-development, innovation and research, and stress-adjustment. To cultivate competent nurses, academic education should emphasize critical thinking skills, integrate problem-based and evidence-based learning approaches into curricula, and use objective structured clinical examination to evaluate learning outcomes. In the healthcare sector, systematic professional training models such as the clinical ladder with multidiscipline rotation hold the potential to train novice nurses as expert professionals. Meanwhile, to advance the professional capabilities of nurses, nursing administrators should provide a positive work environment to fuel and maintain learning motivation. Education and healthcare systems should work closely together to promote the professional competence of nurses and to strengthen the value of the nursing profession (Yu, 2020).

Competency is defined as the application and demonstration of appropriate knowledge, skills, behaviors, and judgment in a clinical setting. Competency is not merely the product of completing required courses, nor is it measured simply by successfully passing a test or completing a checklist. Rather, competency is confirmed when knowledge and skills are accurately applied at the bedside, and appropriate behaviors and judgments are consistently displayed in practice.

Improving safety requires a system culture and mindset that guides a proactive system wide plan to provide care that is safe, reliable and free from harm. Total system safety is interdependent, collaborative and coordinated. High reliability organizations simplify and standardize processes to achieve reliable results. For example, following an evidence-based protocol exactly when inserting and managing central lines has resulted in sharp reductions in infection. Healthcare workers take pride in working in organizations focused on quality and safety. Workers experience satisfaction in doing work well and are supported or restrained by their work environment (Sherwood, 2021).

Health professionals serve as the bridge between patients, the knowledge generated by scientific research, and the policies and practices to implement that knowledge. As the recipients of care, the public trusts health professionals to provide care

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that is safe, efficient, effective, timely, patient-centered, and equitable. Educating professionals about new theories and evidence of what does and does not work, and under what circumstances, is one part of promoting the provision of better health care. Because individual learning styles differ greatly, innovative learning methods are developed to help health professionals maintain their competencies. Over time, learning methods have evolved from a focus on professionals' attendance at and satisfaction with a limited set of educational activities to a focus on demonstrably changing professional practice and improving patient outcomes. Better learning methods need to be developed continuously, as creating appropriate methods, processes, and contexts is imperative for professionals to provide the highest quality care possible (National Library of Medicine, 2022).

Clinical competency has been a challenging issue in nursing profession. The feeling of low competency could decrease job satisfaction and increase occupational withdrawal; it also influences the quality of care. On the contrary, feeling competent could decrease burnout and increase self-confidence. Nursing care in surgical departments needs considerable clinical competencies. Surgery is a traumatic procedure, and patients need special care. Many patients confront complex situations, and nurses should be competent in making urgent and correct clinical decisions in surgical wards. Besides, infection is an important issue in surgical departments and surgical nurses must be competent in implementing infection control strategies (Afshat et al. 2020).

In a study conducted by Istomina et al. 2021 on the competences of nurses, the overall level of nurse competence, and the frequency of using the competencies in practice as perceived by nurses were high. Nurses assessed the competencies in managing situations and work role the highest and in teaching-coaching and ensuring quality the lowest. Sociodemographic factors such as nurse education, experience, professional development, independence, and work satisfaction as well as the evaluation of quality of nursing care were identified as factors associated with nurse competence. The study findings made the assumption that nurse education, nurse experience, and nurse professional development play a significant role in the evaluation of nurse competence as well as the evaluation of quality of nursing care. It is necessary to upgrade nursing education programs at all levels of nursing education in Lithuania: university, non-university, and professional development courses. The qualities of preconditions for nursing care, cooperation with relatives, caring and supporting initiative are related to nurse competence.

Faraji et al. (2019) conducted a study to evaluate the clinical competence and its related demographic factors among critical care nurses in Kermanshah, Iran. In this cross-sectional study, Iranian nurses were selected by stratified random sampling. The mean score of nurses' clinical competence was at a "very good level". The mean score of using clinical competence in practice was at a "good level". Among the subscales of clinical competence, the highest mean score was related to "managing situation". The mean score of "using clinical competence in practice" was related to the subscale of "therapeutic interventions". There was no statistically significant difference among the score of clinical competence of nurses varying with different gender, age, academic degree, and work experience.

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It concluded that the clinical competence of critical care nurses in Kermanshah was at a “very good” level, and the use of clinical competence in practice was at a “good level.” Given the importance of clinical competencies in practice, nurses' clinical competence should be evaluated objectively and positive measures should be taken to promote the application of their clinical competence.

Moreover, Ha et al. (2020) made a study on the factors influencing competency development of nurses as perceived by stakeholders in Vietnam. The research participants described numerous of factors that influence the journey of developing nurses' competencies. The identified factors were relevant to nursing education and training system in Vietnam; working environments of nurses; public image and values of nursing profession; characteristics of nurses themselves; Vietnamese nursing profession sociocultural-economic and political aspects in Vietnam; and global contexts. It concluded that the derived knowledge would greatly benefit clinical nurses, administrators, nursing educators, health care services managers, policy makers as well as other relevant health care stakeholders in proposing of solutions to promote nursing education, nursing workplace environments, and the appropriate regulations in order to enhance the nursing competency and quality of nursing services in Vietnam.

In accordance of Article III, section 9 (c) of Republic Act No. 9173 or the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, this state that the Professional Regulatory Board of Nursing is empowered to “monitor and enforce quality standards of nursing practice in the Philippines and exercise the powers necessary to ensure the maintenance of efficient, ethical and technical, moral and professional standards in the practice of nursing taking into account of the health needs of the nation.” In conclusion, this lead in the improvement and effective implementation of the core competency standards of nursing practice in the Philippines to ensure safe and quality nursing care, and maintain integrity of the nursing profession.

Competencies ensure the right people throughout your clinical workforce are equipped to achieve optimal performance outcomes. Successful competencies align with organizational goals and individual performance evaluations and are used to prevent patient harm while improving clinical outcomes.

Heightened by the complexity of globalization, dynamics of information, technology, demographic changes, health care reforms and increasing demands for quality nursing care for clients, expectations for contemporary nursing practice competencies emerged. As mandated, the Board of Nursing, through a monitoring and evaluation scheme that the competency standards are implemented and utilized effectively in nursing education (BON, 2021).

It is in this context that the researcher was interested to study on the competencies of nurses in the clinical area in different public and private hospitals in Eastern, Pangasinan to assess their competencies.

Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework

The study adapted the theory of Faye Abdellah on the Twenty One Nursing Problems. According to the theory, “Nursing is based on an art and science that mold the

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attitudes, intellectual competencies, and technical skills of the individual nurse into the desire and ability to help people, sick or well, cope with their health needs.”

The patient-centered approach to nursing was developed from Abdellah's practice, and the theory is considered a human needs theory. It was formulated to be an instrument for nursing education, so it most suitable and useful in that field. The nursing model is intended to guide care in hospital institutions.

This study also adapted the theory of Imogene King on Conceptual System and Goal Attainment Theory that deals with the man as a biopsychosocial being. The theory deals to re-establish positive adaptation to his or her environment. She describes nursing as a helping profession that assists individuals and groups in society to attain, maintain and restore health.

Nursing is an interaction process between the client and the nurse whereby during perceiving, setting goals and acting on them, transactions occur and goals are achieved. The goal of nursing is health promotion, maintenance or restoration; care of the sick or injured, and care of the dying. Human beings are the focus of nursing particularly on the fundamental health needs like need for care that seeks to prevent illness and need for care when human beings are unable to help themselves (Bautista, 2010).

It also made use of the Bandura's Social Learning Theory, renamed Social Cognitive Theory, for it is useful in understanding the psychosocial dynamics underlying behaviors. The theory provides a perspective for identifying methods, which can be utilized to promote certain behaviors. The basic premise of Social Cognitive Theory is that the expectation of personal mastery and success influences whether or not an individual will engage in a particular behavior. According to this theory, behavior is determined by expectancies and incentives, as perceived by an individual (Flores, et. al. 2011).

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Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the level of competency of nurses in the different hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- What is the profile of the nurses in terms of the following?
 - age;
 - civil status
 - highest educational attainment;
 - number of years in the nursing service
 - area of assignment, and

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- f. type of hospital facility?
 2. What is the level of competency of nurses along the following areas:
 - a. safe and quality nursing practice;
 - b. management of resources and environment;
 - c. health education;
 - d. legal responsibility;
 - e. ethico-moral responsibility;
 - f. personal and professional development;
 - g. quality improvement;
 - h. research;
 - i. record management;
 - j. communication, and
 - k. collaboration and teamwork?
 3. Is there a significant relationship in the competency of nurses across their profile variables?
 4. Is there a significant difference in the competency of nurses across their profile variables?
 5. What development program may be proposed to enhance the competencies of nurses?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship in the competency of nurses across the respondents' profile.
2. There is no significant difference in the competency of nurses across the respondents' profile.

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Chapter 2 Methodology

This chapter presents the research methodology which includes the discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive method of research with the questionnaire as data gathering tool to assess the level of competency of nurses in the clinical area. According to Best (2015); descriptive research is the process that goes beyond mere gathering and tabulation of data. It involves an element of interpretation of the meaning and the significance of what is described. Thus description is often combined with comparison and contrast involving the measurements, classifications, interpretation and evaluation.

Population and Locale of the Study

The population of the study were the nurses in different public and hospitals of Eastern Pangasinan, They were those assigned in the different wards of the hospitals composed of 60 respondents. To represent the population, purposive sampling was used and was delimited to the nurses who are working in the identified hospitals of Eastern Pangasinan. Hospitals involved were secondary hospitals both public and private.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on the Core competency Standards of the Board of Nursing. Part I focused on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in the nursing service, status of employment, and type of facility. Part II tackled the level of competencies of the nurses based on the core competency standards of nurses along the 11 key areas of responsibility. Part III and Part IV dealt on the significant difference and relationship between the competencies of the nurses across their profile variables. Part V was a proposed development plan to enhance the competencies of nurses.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the actual gathering of data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission is granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher requested and coordinated with the Chief of Hospitals/ Medical Directors for the permission of conducting the study in the respondents' setting. After securing the consent, the researcher proceeded to the respondents. Gathering of data was done personally by the researcher during the scheduled time and date.

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The data that was collected was analyzed, and interpreted to determine the level the competency of nurses in different public and private hospitals.

Treatment of the Data

For Problem No.1 on the respondent's profile, frequency and percentage was used. The frequency determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$$

where: P = percentage

F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

For problem No. 2, on the level of competency of nurses in the different area of responsibility, the weighted mean was used. Weighted mean is the mean of a set of values wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance. This study used a five-point rating scale system, as shown on the table below.

Formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fi}{N}$$

where: \bar{x} = weighted mean

N = total # of population; and

fi = frequencies corresponding to the given items

Literal Value	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Competent
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Competent
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Competent
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Competent
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Competent

For Problem No. 3 and 4 on the significant difference and relationships Analysis of Variance was used to test the difference, whereas Chi-Square was used to test the relationship between variables.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

$$F = \frac{MSb}{MSw}$$

Where:

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MSb-Mean Square Between

MSw-Mean Square Within

Chi-Square

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where: O =observed number of cases

$$E = \frac{(\text{row total})(\text{column total})}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Chapter 3

Results and discussions

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the nurse respondents.

Respondent's Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, employment status, and type of hospital facility.

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that majority of the respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40 years old with a frequency of 35 or 58.3 percent followed by 21-30 years old with a frequency of 19 or 31.7 percent. It revealed that the respondents were young adults. According to Erikson, 31-40 years old are considered young adults. Young adults need to form intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success leads to strong relationships, while failure results in loneliness and isolation. This stage covers the period of early adulthood when people are exploring personal relationships.

Civil status. The majority of the respondents were singles with a frequency of 35 or 58.3 percent followed by married with a frequency of 22 or 36.7 percent. It revealed that the respondents were not yet into marital relationships and pursuing their experiences in their own field of assignment. According to Wikipedia, single is often used to refer to someone who is not involved in either any type of sexual relationship.

Table 1

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Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables

n=60

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	19	31.7
31 – 40	35	58.3
41 – 50	3	5.0
51 and above	3	5.0
Civil Status		
Single	35	58.3
Married	22	36.7
Widow/er	3	5.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	42	70.0
With Masters Units	9	15.0
Master's Degree	9	15.0
With doctorate units		
Number of Years in the Nursing Service		
1 – 3	23	38.3
4 – 6	12	20.0
7 – 10	11	18.3
11 and above	14	23.3
Employment Status		
Regular	29	48.3
Casual	5	8.3
Contractual	14	23.3
Job order	12	20.0
Type of Hospital Facility		
Public	49	81.7
Private	11	18.3

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that majority of the respondents were bachelor's degree holder with a frequency of 42 or 70 percent, followed by those with masteral units and master's degree with a frequency of 9 or 15 percent. It showed that

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majority did not pursue higher level of learning. This might be related to the fact that their salaries are not competitive to some nurses fail to enrol in the masteral or doctoral program. According to Istomina et al. (2021), it is necessary for the nurses to upgrade nursing education programs at all levels of nursing education

Number of years in service. It showed that most respondents were in the service for 1-3 years with a frequency of 23 or 38.3 percent, 11 years and above with a frequency of 14 or 23.3 percent, 4-6 years with a frequency of 12 or 20 percent and 7-10 years with a frequency of 11 or 18.3 percent. It revealed that the respondents were in the service at different number of years and most were in the service for few years and earning their experiences.

Employment status. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents were regular employee with a frequency of 29 or 48.3 percent, contractual with a frequency of 14 or 23.3 percent, Job order with a frequency of 12 or 20 percent, and casual with a frequency of 5 or 8.3 percent. It showed that most nurses were permanent in their position.

Type of hospital facility. It showed that most respondents were employed in public hospital with a frequency of 49 or 81.7 percent, and those in the private health facility with a frequency of 11 or 18.3 percent. It revealed that most respondents were employed in a government facility where most often cater to many patients.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Safe and Quality Practice

Table 2 presents the level of competency of nurses along safe and quality practice.

Table 2

Level of Competency of Nurses along Safe and Quality Practice

n=60

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. identify actual or potential safety risks to clients.	4.62	HC
2. reduce the risk of disease transmission by doing frequency hand washing.	4.67	HC
3. encourage client's use of safety measures to prevent injury.	4.67	HC
4. modify interventions to suit client's situation by selecting interventions that are consistent with client's identified concerns and priorities.	4.57	HC
5. implement strategies to prevent communicable diseases such as wearing face masks and gloves.	4.62	HC

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6. promote health practice such as daily exercise for a healthy body.	4.55	HC
7. implement preventative strategies related to safe use of medication such as asking a written information about the side effects of the client's medication to the pharmacist.	4.63	HC
8. collaborate with client to prioritize needs and develop risk prevention strategies.	4.58	HC
9. select interventions consistent with client identified concerns and priorities such as establishing rapport to gain trust of the client.	4.67	HC
10. adapt assessment to client's situation like assessing if the client has AV fistula on her right or left forearm.	4.55	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.61	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicators are items numbers 2, 3, and 9 “reduce the risk of disease transmission by doing frequency hand washing,” “encourage client's use of safety measures to prevent injury,” and “select interventions consistent with client identified concerns and priorities such as establishing rapport to gain trust of the client,” with a weighted mean of 4.67 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses maintained their utmost care to their patients, since one of the goals of nursing is to give quality patient care. According to Yu, 2020, core competency is vital to the nursing profession. It helps guarantee the high quality, and effective delivery of care, and maintains the social value, and status of the nursing profession. The core competency profile for the nursing profession embraces basic behavioral attributes as well as mastery of advanced practice skills.

The lowest indicators is item number 6 and 10, “promote health practice such as daily exercise for a healthy body,” and “adapt assessment to client's situation like assessing if the client has AV fistula on her right or left forearm” with a weighted mean of 4.55 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses showed the proper competency in other areas of care.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along safe and quality practice got an average weighted mean of 4.61 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses were equipped with the competencies along safe and quality practice. According to Yu, (2020) competency is confirmed when knowledge and skills are accurately applied

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at the bedside, and appropriate behavior and judgments are consistently displayed in practice.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Management of Resources and Environment

Table 3 presents the level of competency of nurses along management of resources and environment..

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicators are items numbers 4 and 8 “calculate medications dosage correctly,” and “provide effective and efficient care,” with a weighted mean of 4.68, and 4.70 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses were knowledgeable on how medications are prepared and administered to patients and the provision of effective care. As mentioned by (Afshat et al. 2020) clinical competency has been a challenging issue in nursing profession. Feeling competent could decrease burnout and increase self-confidence. Patients are confronted with complex situations, and nurses should be competent in making urgent and correct clinical decisions.

Table 3

Level of Competency of Nurses along Management of Resources and Environment

n=60

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. intervene in response to changes observed in client's condition.	4.62	HC
2. manage multiple nursing interventions simultaneously.	4.50	HC
3. administer medications safely and appropriately.	4.65	HC
4. calculate medications dosage correctly.	4.68	HC
5. check drainage tubes and collection devices.	4.62	HC
6. maintain a caring environment that assists client.	4.58	HC
7. arrange for adaptations in environment to facilitate client's development of independence in activities of daily living.	4.65	HC
8. provide effective and efficient care.	4.70	HC
9. modify plan of care to suit client's changing situation.	4.58	HC
10. implement preventive strategies related to environmental safety like raising the side rails of the bed to prevent accidental falls.	4.58	HC

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Average Weighted Mean

4.62

HC

Legend:

Statistical Range

4.50 – 5.00

3.50 – 4.49

2.50 – 3.49

1.50 – 2.49

1.00 – 1.49

Descriptive Equivalent

Highly Competent (HC)

Competent (C)

Moderately Competent (MC)

Slightly Competent (SC)

Not Competent (NC)

The lowest indicator is item number 2, “manage multiple nursing interventions simultaneously.” with a weighted mean of 4.50 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses were equally equipped with the necessary competencies when it comes to management of environment and resources.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along management of environment and resources got an average weighted mean of 4.62 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses give effective and efficient care to their clients. According to Sherwood, (2021) improving safety requires a system culture and mindset that guides a proactive system wide plan to provide care that is safe, reliable and free from harm. Total system safety is interdependent, collaborative and coordinated.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Health Education

Table 4 presents the level of competency of nurses along health education.

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicator is item number 6 “help the client understand interventions and their relationship to expected outcomes” with a weighted mean of 4.68, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses perform their interventions well for better patient care outcomes. According to the Library of Medicine (2022), the recipients of care, the public trusts health professionals provide care that is safe, efficient, effective, timely, patient-centered, and equitable. Educating professionals about new theories and evidence of what does and does not work, and under what circumstances, is one part of promoting the provision of better health care. Because individual learning styles differ greatly, innovative learning methods are developed to help health professionals maintain their competencies.

The lowest indicators are item numbers 4 and 5, “provide nursing care to prevent development of complications that can impede recovery such as monitoring blood glucose level to client’s with diabetic mellitus,” and “assist the client with reintegration into family and community networks with a weighted mean of 4.53 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses monitor and assist their patients well so that complications will not arise for their full recovery. They give the necessary health education for shorter stay in the hospital.

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Table 4

Level of Competency of Nurses along Health Education

n=60

Indicators l...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. help the client to understand preventable health problems such as hypertension, obesity and cancer and explain their consequences.	4.63	HC
2. assist the client to understand the link between health promotion strategies and health outcomes.	4.55	HC
3. use evidence-based knowledge from nursing, health sciences, and related disciplines in the provision of individualized nursing care.	4.55	HC
4. provide nursing care to prevent development of complications that can impede recovery such as monitoring blood glucose level to client's with diabetic mellitus.	4.53	HC
5. assist the client with reintegration into family and community networks.	4.53	HC
6. help the client understand interventions and their relationship to expected outcomes.	4.68	HC
7. use principles of teaching and learning with client receiving curative/ supportive care.	4.62	HC
8. encourage family and significant others to support client during the rehabilitation process.	4.63	HC
9. evaluate and respond appropriately to status of client in relation to anticipated outcomes.	4.58	HC
10. collaborate with clients to reduce complex health risks like developing disease complications.	4.63	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.60	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

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Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along health education got an average weighted mean of 4.60 or "Highly Competent." It connotes that the nurses are knowledgeable in giving advises and health teachings to their clients.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Legal Responsibility

Table 5 presents the level of competency of nurses along legal responsibility.

Table 5

Level of Competency of Nurses along Legal Responsibility

n=60

Indicators I...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. validate data with client and or significant others.	4.67	HC
2. practice in a manner consistent with acts governing nursing practice, the regulatory body's standards for nursing and guidelines for the scope of nursing practice.	4.65	HC
3. practice in a manner consistent with common law and legislation that directs quality nursing.	4.72	HC
4. exercise professional judgement when following agency procedures, protocols or position statements.	4.65	HC
5. exercise professional judgement in the absence of agency procedures, protocols or position statements.	4.58	HC
6. practice in a manner consistent with professional values, principles of safety and obligation to take action.	4.68	HC
7. advocate for the client or client's representative, especially when the client is unable to advocate for self like when he/she is mentally incapacitated.	4.55	HC
8. used established communication protocols within the health care agency, across agencies and health system.	4.65	HC
9. make sure the environment is conducive to safe, competent and ethical care.	4.65	HC
10. support client to draw on own assets and resources in meeting self-care needs.	4.63	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.64	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)

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1.50 – 2.49 Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49 Not Competent (NC)

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicator is item number “practice in a manner consistent with common law and legislation that directs quality nursing” with a weighted mean of 4.72, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses conform with the law that regulates the nursing practice. One way of showing conformity with the law is having an updated license to practice the nursing profession.

The lowest indicator is item number 7, “advocate for the client or client's representative, especially when the client is unable to advocate for self like when he/she is mentally incapacitated,” with a weighted mean of 4.55 or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses give their utmost care even when no relative is present, they still perform what is due to all patients under their care.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along legal responsibility got an average weighted mean of 4.64 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses are aware of their legal responsibilities in their profession. Ha et al. (2020) in their study concluded that the derived knowledge would greatly benefit clinical nurses, administrators, nursing educators, health care services managers, policy makers as well as other relevant health care stakeholders in proposing of solutions to promote nursing education, nursing workplace environments, and the appropriate regulations in order to enhance the nursing competency and quality of nursing services. This is also true to our nurses that they must comply with necessary regulations in the practice of their profession.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Ethico-Moral Responsibility

Table 6 presents the level of competency of nurses along ethico-moral responsibility..

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicator is item number 6 “demonstrate respect for colleagues” with a weighted mean of 4.72, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses gives due respect to their colleagues and other members of the health team.

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Table 6

Level of Competency of Nurses along Ethico-Moral Responsibility

n=60

Indicators l...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. maintain clear, concise, accurate, and timely record of client care.	4.68	HC
2. recognize limitations of own competence and seek assistance when necessary.	4.63	HC
3. identify an unrealistic workload and seek and seek assistance as necessary.	4.55	HC
4. delegate health care activities to others consistent with levels of expertise, education, job description/agency policy, and client needs.	4.58	HC
5. accept responsibility for own action and decisions when delegating.	4.67	HC
6. demonstrate respect for colleagues.	4.72	HC
7. clarify nurses role and responsibilities to other health care team members.	4.62	HC
8. used established communication protocols within the health care agency, across agencies and health system.	4.60	HC
9. provide constructive feedback to colleagues.	4.52	HC
10. use conflict resolution skills to facilitate health team interactions.	4.53	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.61	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

The lowest indicator are item numbers 9 and 10, “provide constructive feedback to colleagues” with a weighted mean of 4.52, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses deal with their colleagues well and gives them feedback in such a way for the betterment of the profession.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along ethico-moral responsibility got an average weighted mean of 4.61 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses

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showed nice camaraderie with their co-workers and work as a team for better care outcomes.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Personal and Professional Development

Table 7 presents the level of competency of nurses along personal and professional development.

Table 7

Level of Competency of Nurses along Personal and Professional Development

n=60

Indicators I...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. hold myself and others accountable for actions and outcomes.	4.63	HC
2. assist client in implementing learning plans such as making a routine health check-ups.	4.60	HC
3. coach others in developing their own career plans.	4.57	HC
4. develop own career plan and measure progress according to plan.	4.67	HC
5. create an environment wherein professional and personal growth is an expectation.	4.63	HC
6. articulate the application of ethical principles to operations.	4.55	HC
7. integrate high ethical standards and core values into everyday work activities.	4.65	HC
8. assure that ethical perspective is included in organizational decisions.	4.58	HC
9. participate in at least one professional organization like Philippine Nurses Association.	4.63	HC
10. support and encourage others to be member in a professional organization like Philippine Nurses Association	4.63	HC
	Average Weighted Mean	HC
	4.62	

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)

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1.00 – 1.49 Not Competent (NC)

All the indicators were rated “Highly Competent,” however, the highest indicator is item number 4 “develop own career plan and measure progress according to plan” with a weighted mean of 4.67, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses have their own way of maintaining their personal and professional career. This is required since in the renewal of professional licence, a nurse must have the required number of continuing professional development units. Istomina et al. (2021) mentioned that nurse professional development play a significant role in the evaluation of nurse competence.

The lowest indicator is item numbers 6, “articulate the application of ethical principles to operations” with a weighted mean of 4.55, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses observe the proper ethical standards in their profession and in their daily duties in the hospital.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along personal and professional development got an average weighted mean of 4.62 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses are practicing what is required of the profession either for personal and professional development. Professional development transcends both concepts and includes areas such as self-directed learning, systems changes, and quality improvement; it teaches people not only how to apply solutions but also how to focus on actual performance and how to identify problems (National Library of Medicine, 2022).

Level of Competency of Nurses along Quality Improvement

Table 8 presents the level of competency of nurses along quality improvement.

All the indicators were rated “Highly competent,” however, the highest indicator is item number 1, “determine patient care quality improvement goals and objectives” with a weighted mean of 4.63, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses were aware of the goals and objectives in giving quality care to patients. It is one of the goals of nursing to give quality care to clients. The Professional Regulatory Board of Nursing monitor and enforce quality standards of nursing practice in the Philippines, which lead in the improvement and effective implementation of the core competency standards of nursing practice to ensure safe and quality nursing care, and maintain integrity of the nursing profession.

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Table 8

Level of Competency of Nurses along Quality Improvement

n=60

Indicators l...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. determine patient care quality improvement goals and objectives.	4.63	HC
2. measures success at improving specific areas of patient care.	4.62	HC
3. analyse the root cause or variation from quality standards.	4.60	HC
4. control solutions and sustain success.	4.60	HC
5. articulate the organization quality improvement program and goals.	4.58	HC
6. explain and utilize metrics as a unit of measure for any process.	4.53	HC
7. integrate high ethical standards and core values into everyday work activities.	4.62	HC
8. assure that ethical perspective is included in organizational decisions.	4.55	HC
9. participate in at least one professional organization like Philippine Nurses Association or Philippine Red Cross.	4.58	HC
10. support and encourage others to participate in a professional organization like Philippine Nurses Association and Philippine Red Cross.	4.52	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.58	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

The lowest indicator is item numbers 6, “articulate the application of ethical principles to operations” with a weighted mean of 4.55, or “Highly Competent.” It showed that the nurses observe the proper ethical standards in their profession and in their daily duties in the hospital.

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Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along quality improvement got an average weighted mean of 4.58 or "Highly Competent." It connotes that the nurses only give the best care and services to their patients for better patient satisfaction.

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Level of Competency of Nurses along Research

Table 9 presents the level of competency of nurses along research.

Table 9

Level of Competency of Nurses along Research

n=60

Indicators I...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. collaborate with nursing faculty in nursing research and incorporate nursing research into practice.	4.38	C
2. incorporate research findings about health risks and risks reduction into plan of care.	4.43	C
3. participate in research which provides outcome measurement.	4.38	C
4. utilize research findings for establishment of standards, practices, and patient care models in the organization.	4.47	C
5. demonstrate awareness of societal and technological trends, issues and new developments as they apply to nursing.	4.52	HC
6. determine when new delivery models are appropriate, and then envision and develop them.	4.45	C
7. update their knowledge and skills through research.	4.47	C
8. participate in studies which provide outcome measurement like joining the research team of the hospital.	4.45	C
9. teach and mentor others to routinely utilize evidence-based data and research.	4.42	C
10. participate in the research planning, implementing, and evaluating changes that affect nursing practice, client care, and the practice environment.	4.50	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.45	C

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)

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1.00 – 1.49 Not Competent (NC)

Along this area is different from the other areas of competency. The highest indicator is on item number 5 and 10 “demonstrate awareness of societal and technological trends, issues and new developments as they apply to nursing,” and “participate in the research planning, implementing, and evaluating changes that affect nursing practice, client care, and the practice environment with a weighted mean of 4.50 and 4.52, or “Highly Competent.” It revealed that the nurses were aware of the technological advances in patient care and they were involved in research planning in their own institutions.

The lowest indicator is item numbers 1 and 3, “collaborate with nursing faculty in nursing research and incorporate nursing research into practice,” and “participate in research which provides outcome measurement,” with a weighted mean of 4.38, or “Competent.” It showed that the nurses incorporate research findings in their clinical practice.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along research got an average weighted mean of 4.45 or “Competent.” It connotes that the nurses based on the findings need a lot more to improve in this area.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Record Management

Table 10 presents the level of competency of nurses along record management.

Along this area is different from the other areas of competency. The highest indicator is on item number 9 “document the plan of care for the clients,” with a weighted mean of 4.67, or “Highly Competent.” It revealed that the nurses follow the proper documentation of care in the clinical area. The data in the charts are good evidences on patient care.

The lowest indicator is item numbers 1 and 2, “evaluate patient care processes and systems,” and “use applications for structured data entry (classification systems, acuity level, etc.),” with a weighted mean of 4.47 and 4.48, or “Competent.” It showed that the nurses were aware that records are important aspects in nursing care for this will help them in cases when something happen to their client in the hospital.

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Table 10

Level of Competency of Nurses along Record Management

n=60

Indicators l...	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. evaluate patient care processes and systems.	4.47	C
2. use applications for structured data entry (classification systems, acuity level, etc.).	4.48	C
3. demonstrate proficient awareness of legal and ethical issues related to client data, information and confidentiality.	4.55	HC
4. utilize hospital database management, decision support database management, decision support and expert system's programs to access information and analyse data from disparate sources for use in planning for patient care processes and systems.	4.50	HC
5. use appropriate techniques for data collection.	4.60	HC
6. collect data about various dimensions of the client.	4.55	HC
7. collect data from a range of appropriate sources.	4.58	HC
8. record and manage the client's data with strict confidentiality.	4.63	HC
9. document the plan of care for the clients.	4.67	HC
10. record client's participation in implementation of plan of care.	4.65	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.57	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent(C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along record management got an average weighted mean of 4.57 or "Highly Competent." It connotes that the nurses perform well in this area of competency.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Communication

Table 11 presents the level of competency of nurses along communication.

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Along this area is different from the other areas of competency. The highest indicator is on item number 7 “inform the physicians to determine patient care equipment and facility needs,” with a weighted mean of 4.67, or “Highly Competent.” It revealed that the nurses have an open communication with the doctors regarding the conditions of their patients. There should always be collaboration with the nurses and doctors.

Table 11

Level of Competency of Nurses along Communication

n=60

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. make oral presentation to diverse audiences on nursing, health care, and organizational issues.	4.50	HC
2. communicate tactfully in such a way to maintain credibility.	4.58	HC
3. inform the patients about the status of their health.	4.48	C
4. manage consultation with the community and business leaders regarding nursing and health care.	4.52	HC
5. manage and address inappropriate behaviour towards patients and staff.	4.57	HC
6. talk with medical staff leaders in determining needed patient care services.	4.53	HC
7. inform the physicians to determine patient care equipment and facility needs.	4.62	HC
8. organize communication group involving physicians and nurses or other discipline.	4.55	HC
9. determine current and future supply and demand for nursing care.	4.52	HC
10. collaborate with nursing programs to provide required resources.	4.48	C
Average Weighted Mean	4.54	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

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The lowest indicator are item numbers 1 and 2, "evaluate patient care processes and systems," and "use applications for structured data entry (classification systems, acuity level, etc.)," with a weighted mean of 4.47 and 4.48, or "Competent." It showed that the nurses were aware that records are important aspects in nursing care for this will help them in cases when something happen to their client in the hospital.

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along record management got an average weighted mean of 4.57 or "Highly Competent." It connotes that the nurses perform well in this area of competency. Faraji et al. (2019) corroborated with the present study that the importance of clinical competencies in practice, nurses' clinical competence should be evaluated objectively and positive measures should be taken to promote the application of their clinical competence.

Level of Competency of Nurses along Collaboration and Teamwork

Table 12 presents the level of competency of nurses along collaboration and teamwork.

All the indicators were rated "Highly competent," however, the highest indicator is item number 9 and 10, "respects the role of other members of the health team," and "act as advocate/ liason of the client during decision making by the interprofessional team," with a weighted mean of 4.70 and 4.73, or "Highly Competent." It showed that the nurses had a good relationship with other members of the health team/ Teamwork in the clinical area is an important aspect for better patient care.

The lowest indicator is item number 4, "assess clients' participatory capacity," with a weighted mean of 4.60, or "Highly Competent." It showed that the nurses involve the patient in his care to make him understand his condition and thereby cooperates in his care.

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Table 12

Level of Competency of Nurses along Collaboration and Teamwork

n=60

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. establishes collaborative relationships with colleagues and other members of the health team to enhance nursing and other health services	4.67	HC
2. utilizes appropriate mechanism for networking, linkage building and referrals	4.67	HC
3. manages a community/village based health facility/component of a health program or nursing service	4.65	HC
4. assess clients' participatory capacity	4.60	HC
5. carries out appropriate strategies to ensure participation of client	4.62	HC
6. Handle/ address issues and conflicts as option for collaboration and shared responsibility for decision making by generating new ways of analysing situations or problems	4.60	HC
7. articulate commitment and opportunities for community involvement on health resource availability access/use	4.60	HC
8. maintain good interpersonal relationship interagency and intraagency	4.68	HC
9. respects the role of other members of the health team	4.72	HC
10. act as advocate/ liason of the client during decision making by the interprofessional team	4.70	HC
Average Weighted Mean	4.65	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

Overall, the level of competency of the nurses along teamwork and collaboration got an average weighted mean of 4.65 or “Highly Competent.” It connotes that the nurses maintain their good working relationship with the health team.

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Level of Competency of Nurses

Table 13 presents the level of competency among the nurses. Ten (10) of the core competencies of the nurse were rated "Highly Competent." The highest indicators are on Collaboration and Teamwork, legal responsibility, Personal and Professional Development and Management of Resources and Environment with a weighted mean of 4.65, 4.64, and 4.62 or "Highly competent,"

Table 13

Level of Competency of Nurses

n=60

Aspect	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Safe and Quality Practice	4.61	HC
Management of Resources and Environment	4.62	HC
Health Education	4.60	HC
Legal Responsibility	4.64	HC
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	4.61	HC
Personal and Professional Development	4.62	HC
Quality Improvement	4.58	HC
Research	4.45	C
Record Management	4.57	HC
Communication	4.54	HC
Collaboration and Teamwork	4.65	HC
Overall Weighted Mean	4.59	HC

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
3.50 – 4.49	Competent (C)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Competent (MC)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Competent (SC)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Competent (NC)

It revealed that these competencies are the strongest among the nurses. In accordance of Article III, section 9 (c) of Republic Act No. 9173 or the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, states that the Professional Regulatory Board of Nursing is empowered to "monitor and enforce quality standards of nursing practice in the Philippines and exercise the powers necessary to ensure the maintenance of efficient, ethical and technical, moral and professional standards in the practice of nursing taking into account of the health needs of the nation

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The lowest indicators are on research, communication, record management and quality improvement with a weighted mean of 4.45, 4.54, 4.57, and 4.65, or “Competent and Highly Competent.” It connotes that these areas must be improved to improve their competency level in rendering patient care.

Overall, the competency level among the nurses got an overall weighted mean of 4.59 or “Highly Competent.” It revealed that the nurses had the different competencies, however, some areas are to be improved to make sure that patients get the best of care from the health care providers. As mandated, the Board of Nursing, through a monitoring and evaluation scheme that the competency standards are implemented and utilized effectively in nursing education (BON, 2021).

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Age

Table 14 presents the difference in the level of competency of nurses across age.

The computed F-values with their corresponding significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance suggest that there exists no significant difference in the level of competency of the nurses when they are grouped according to age. This means that the level of competency of the nurses along the 11 aspects are comparable regardless of their age.

Table 14

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Between Groups	.684	3	.228	.662	.579	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.278	56	.344			
	Total	19.962	59				
Management of Resources and Environment	Between Groups	1.019	3	.340	1.054	.376	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.044	56	.322			
	Total	19.063	59				
Health Education	Between Groups	.839	3	.280	.746	.530	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.009	56	.375			
	Total	21.849	59				
Legal Responsibility	Between Groups	1.302	3	.434	1.538	.215	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.805	56	.282			
	Total	17.107	59				
	Between Groups	1.850	3	.617	2.103	.110	

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Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Within Groups	16.424	56	.293			Not Significant
	Total	18.274	59				
Personal and Professional Development	Between Groups	.835	3	.278	.841	.477	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.522	56	.331			
	Total	19.357	59				
Quality Improvement	Between Groups	2.241	3	.747	2.406	.077	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.383	56	.310			
	Total	19.623	59				
Research	Between Groups	2.089	3	.696	1.369	.262	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.480	56	.509			
	Total	30.569	59				
Record Management	Between Groups	1.837	3	.612	1.551	.211	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.113	56	.395			
	Total	23.950	59				
Communication	Between Groups	2.558	3	.853	2.147	.104	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.238	56	.397			
	Total	24.797	59				
Collaboration and Teamwork	Between Groups	2.199	3	.733	2.474	.071	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.591	56	.296			
	Total	18.790	59				

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Faraji et al. (2019) have similar findings in their study that there was no statistically significant difference among the score of clinical competence of nurses varying with different gender, age, academic degree, and work experience.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Civil Status

Table 15 shows the difference in the level of competency of nurses across civil status. The computed F-values along all the 11 areas being considered have generated significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance.

This implies that the civil status of the nurses did not cause any variation in their level of competencies along the given 11 areas. Therefore, single, married and widow/er nurses have the same level of competency along safe and quality practice, management of resources and environment, health education, legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, research, record management, communication and collaboration and teamwork.

Table 15

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Civil Status

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Between Groups	.512	2	.256	.750	.477	Not Significant
	Within Groups	19.450	57	.341			
	Total	19.962	59				
Management of Resources and Environment	Between Groups	.464	2	.232	.712	.495	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.599	57	.326			
	Total	19.063	59				
Health Education	Between Groups	.589	2	.294	.789	.459	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.260	57	.373			
	Total	21.849	59				
Legal Responsibility	Between Groups	.519	2	.260	.892	.415	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.588	57	.291			
	Total	17.107	59				
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Between Groups	.849	2	.424	1.389	.258	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.425	57	.306			
	Total	18.274	59				
Personal and Professional Development	Between Groups	.661	2	.331	1.008	.371	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.695	57	.328			
	Total	19.357	59				
	Between Groups	1.534	2	.767	2.417	.098	

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Quality Improvement	Within Groups	18.089	57	.317			Not Significant
	Total	19.623	59				
Research	Between Groups	1.830	2	.915	1.814	.172	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.740	57	.504			
	Total	30.569	59				
Record Management	Between Groups	.914	2	.457	1.131	.330	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.036	57	.404			
	Total	23.950	59				
Communication	Between Groups	1.250	2	.625	1.513	.229	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.546	57	.413			
	Total	24.797	59				
Collaboration and Teamwork	Between Groups	.685	2	.342	1.077	.347	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.105	57	.318			
	Total	18.790	59				

This implies that the civil status of the nurses did not cause any variation in their level of competencies along the given 11 areas. Therefore, single, married and widow/er nurses have the same level of competency along safe and quality practice, management of resources and environment, health education, legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, research, record management, communication and collaboration and teamwork.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Highest Educational Attainment

Table 16 provides the data on the difference in the level of competency of nurses across highest educational attainment. Based on the computed F-values and significance values, there exist no significant differences along safe and quality practice, ethico-moral responsibility, quality improvement, research, record management, communication, and collaboration and teamwork.

Results suggest that significant differences in the level of competency of the nurses exist along management of resources, health education, legal responsibility, and personal and professional development. However, when Scheffe Test was further employed to check on the groups that have shown significant differences on these specific areas, the data revealed no significant differences. Hence, it is safe to claim that there is no enough evidence to for differences in the level of competency of the nurses when compared based on their educational attainment.

Highest educational attainment does not cause differences in the level of competency of the nurses in all the 11 areas being considered in this study.

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Table 16

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Between Groups	1.662	2	.831	2.589	.084	Not Significant
	Within Groups	18.300	57	.321			
	Total	19.962	59				
Management of Resources and Environment	Between Groups	2.022	2	1.011	3.382	.041	Significant
	Within Groups	17.041	57	.299			
	Total	19.063	59				
Health Education	Between Groups	3.142	2	1.571	4.787	.012	Significant
	Within Groups	18.706	57	.328			
	Total	21.849	59				
Legal Responsibility	Between Groups	1.924	2	.962	3.611	.033	Significant
	Within Groups	15.183	57	.266			
	Total	17.107	59				
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Between Groups	1.648	2	.824	2.826	.068	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.626	57	.292			
	Total	18.274	59				
Personal and Professional Development	Between Groups	2.045	2	1.022	3.366	.042	Significant
	Within Groups	17.312	57	.304			
	Total	19.357	59				
Quality Improvement	Between Groups	1.654	2	.827	2.624	.081	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.969	57	.315			
	Total	19.623	59				
Research	Between Groups	2.656	2	1.328	2.711	.075	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.914	57	.490			
	Total	30.569	59				
Record Management	Between Groups	2.350	2	1.175	3.100	.053	Not Significant
	Within Groups	21.600	57	.379			
	Total	23.950	59				
Communication	Between Groups	2.420	2	1.210	3.082	.054	Not Significant
	Within Groups	22.377	57	.393			
	Total	24.797	59				
Collaboration and Teamwork	Between Groups	1.462	2	.731	2.405	.099	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.328	57	.304			
	Total	18.790	59				

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Number of Years in the Nursing Service

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Table 17 presents the difference in the level of competency of nurses across number of years in the nursing service. The computed F-values along safe and quality practice, health education, and research suggest insignificant results as indicated in the significance values which are higher than .05.

Table 17

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Number of Years in the Nursing Service

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Between Groups	2.294	3	.765	2.424	.075	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.668	56	.315			
	Total	19.962	59				
Management of Resources and Environment	Between Groups	2.543	3	.848	2.873	.044	Significant
	Within Groups	16.520	56	.295			
	Total	19.063	59				
Health Education	Between Groups	1.845	3	.615	1.722	.173	Not Significant
	Within Groups	20.003	56	.357			
	Total	21.849	59				
Legal Responsibility	Between Groups	3.218	3	1.073	4.325	.008	Significant
	Within Groups	13.889	56	.248			
	Total	17.107	59				
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Between Groups	3.341	3	1.114	4.176	.010	Significant
	Within Groups	14.933	56	.267			
	Total	18.274	59				
Personal and Professional Development	Between Groups	3.071	3	1.024	3.519	.021	Significant
	Within Groups	16.286	56	.291			
	Total	19.357	59				
Quality Improvement	Between Groups	3.942	3	1.314	4.692	.005	Significant
	Within Groups	15.682	56	.280			
	Total	19.623	59				
Research	Between Groups	2.859	3	.953	1.926	.136	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.710	56	.495			
	Total	30.569	59				
Record Management	Between Groups	4.597	3	1.532	4.434	.007	Significant
	Within Groups	19.353	56	.346			
	Total	23.950	59				
Communication	Between Groups	4.910	3	1.637	4.608	.006	Significant
	Within Groups	19.887	56	.355			
	Total	24.797	59				

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Collaboration and Teamwork	Between Groups	3.400	3	1.133	4.123	.010	Significant
	Within Groups	15.390	56	.275			
	Total	18.790	59				

Meanwhile, significant differences exist along management of resources and environment, legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, record management, communication, and collaboration and teamwork. Hence, the need for further test, that is, Scheffe test, with results shown on the next table.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Number of Years in the Nursing Service

Table 18 reveals the data which verifies the existence of significant differences in the level of competency of the nurses across number of years in the nursing service. The test confirms that 7 out of the detected 8 areas have really shown significant differences.

Table 18

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Number of Years in the Nursing Service

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Legal Responsibility	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.579	.013
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.589	.015
Personal and Professional Development	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.550	.037
Quality Improvement	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.636	.010
Record Management	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.676	.014
Communication	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.607	.038
Collaboration and Teamwork	1-3 vs 11 & above	-.609	.013

The differences exist between nurses who have been in the service for 1-3 years, and those who have served for at least 11 years. The significant negative mean differences indicate that the nurses who have served for 11 years and above have higher level of competency as compared to those who are 1-3 years in the service. This means that the nurses with longer years of service have higher level of competency along legal responsibility, ethico-moral responsibility, personal and professional development, quality improvement, record management, communication, and collaboration and teamwork.

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ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Employment Status

Table 19 shows the difference in the level of competency of nurses across employment status.

Table 19

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Employment Status

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Between Groups	2.982	3	.994	3.278	.027	Significant
	Within Groups	16.980	56	.303			
	Total	19.962	59				
Management of Resources and Environment	Between Groups	4.070	3	1.357	5.067	.004	Significant
	Within Groups	14.994	56	.268			
	Total	19.063	59				
Health Education	Between Groups	3.168	3	1.056	3.166	.031	Significant
	Within Groups	18.690	56	.334			
	Total	21.849	59				
Legal Responsibility	Between Groups	2.684	3	.895	3.473	.022	Significant
	Within Groups	14.424	56	.258			
	Total	17.107	59				
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Between Groups	4.435	3	1.478	5.982	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	13.839	56	.247			
	Total	18.274	59				
Personal and Professional Development	Between Groups	2.568	3	.856	2.855	.045	Significant
	Within Groups	16.788	56	.300			
	Total	19.357	59				
Quality Improvement	Between Groups	5.111	3	1.704	6.574	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	14.512	56	.259			
	Total	19.623	59				
Research	Between Groups	4.681	3	1.560	3.375	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	25.889	56	.462			
	Total	30.569	59				
Record Management	Between Groups	4.802	3	1.601	4.681	.005	Significant
	Within Groups	19.148	56	.342			
	Total	23.950	59				
Communication	Between Groups	5.030	3	1.677	4.750	.005	Significant
	Within Groups	19.767	56	.353			
	Total	24.797	59				

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Collaboration and Teamwork	Between Groups	4.671	3	1.557	6.175	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	14.119	56	.252			
	Total	18.790	59				

All the computed F-values in the 11 areas have significance values which are lower than the set .05 level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. There exists a significant difference in the level of competency of the nurses especially if they are grouped according to their employment status.

The results of the Scheffe Test is displayed in the next table.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Employment Status

Table 20 reveals the groups which differ in the level of competency. Scheffe Test confirms 9 out of the 11 areas with significant results.

Table 20

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Employment Status

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Safe and Quality Practice	Job order vs regular	-.557	.043
Management of Resources & Environment	Job order vs contractual	-.698	.013
	Job order vs regular	-.628	.010
Health Education	Job order vs regular	-.585	.043
Legal Responsibility	Job order vs regular	-.522	.038
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Job order vs contractual	-.662	.015
	Job order vs regular	-.689	.002
Quality Improvement	Job order vs contractual	-.743	.006
	Job order vs regular	-.728	.002
Record Management	Job order vs regular	-.736	.007
Communication	Job order vs regular	-.753	.006
Collaboration and Teamwork	Job order vs contractual	-.657	.017
	Job order vs regular	-.724	.001

A certain trend is evident in the groups being compared: between nurses under job order and regular nurses; and job orders contractual nurses. All mean differences are negative, hence, the second set in the compared groups have higher mean values.

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This indicates that the nurses with regular and contractual status have considered themselves more competent than the nurses who work under job order.

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Type of Hospital Facility

Table 21 reveals the results of the t-Test on the difference in the level of competency of the nurses across type of hospital facility. The computed t-values were provided with significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance.

Table 21

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Level of Competency of Nurses across Type of Hospital Facility

Aspect	Type of Hospital Facility	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Safe and Quality Practice	Public	49	4.61	-.019	.196	58	-.098	.923	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.63						
Management of Resources	Public	49	4.66	.210	.189	58	1.108	.273	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.45						
Health Education	Public	49	4.66	.339	.200	58	1.696	.095	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.32						
Legal Responsibility	Public	49	4.69	.276	.178	58	1.553	.126	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.42						
Ethico-Moral Responsibility	Public	49	4.63	.112	.187	58	.602	.549	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.52						
Personal And Professional Dev't	Public	49	4.65	.208	.191	58	1.088	.281	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.45						
Quality Improvement	Public	49	4.62	.180	.193	58	.934	.354	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.44						
Research	Public	49	4.50	.280	.239	58	1.169	.247	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.22						
Record Management	Public	49	4.60	.150	.213	58	.705	.484	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.45						
Communication	Public	49	4.59	.277	.215	58	1.286	.204	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.31						
Collaboration and Teamwork	Public	49	4.69	.228	.188	58	1.217	.229	Not Significant
	Private	11	4.46						

This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. There exists no significant difference in the level of competency of the nurses when grouped in terms of type of

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hospital facility. This means that the type of hospital facility the nurses are assigned into does not affect their competence in performing well in the different areas.

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Relationship Between the Level of Competency of Nurses and their Profile Variables

Table 22 provides the data on the relationship between the level of competency of nurses and their profile variables. The results clearly show that the level of competency of the nurses is not significantly related to age and type of hospital facility.

Table 22

Relationship Between the Level of Competency of Nurses and their Profile Variables

Profile Variables	A		B		C		D		E		F	
	r-value	Sig										
Age	.099	.451	.132	.316	.190	.146	.116	.377	.169	.198	.154	.240
Civil Status	.146	.267	.123	.349	.155	.238	.171	.192	.215	.098	.186	.161
Highest Educational Attainment	.288*	.025	.326*	.011	.356*	.005	.330*	.010	.283*	.029	.325*	.011
Number of Years in the Nursing Service	.324*	.011	.359*	.005	.288*	.025	.434*	.001	.423*	.001	.397*	.002
Employment Status	.289*	.025	.313*	.015	.304*	.018	.283*	.028	.385*	.002	.214	.100
Type of Hospital Facility	-.013	.923	.144	.273	.217	.095	.200	.126	.079	.549	.141	.281

Significant at .05 level

Legend:

A - Safe and Quality Practice

G - Quality Improvement

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- | | |
|---|--------------------------------|
| B - Management of Resources and Environment | H - Research |
| C - Health Education | I - Record Management |
| D - Legal Responsibility | J - Communication |
| E - Ethico-Moral Responsibility | K - Collaboration and Teamwork |
| F - Personal and Professional Development | |

Continuation of Table 23

	G		H		I		J		K	
	r-value	sig								
Profile Variables	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Age	.232	.075	.171	.192	.208	.111	.245	.059	.146	.265
Civil Status	.272*	.036	.244	.060	.195	.135	.224	.085	.191	.144
Highest Educational Attainment	.246	.058	.295*	.022	.312*	.015	.303*	.019	.276*	.033
Number of Years in the Nursing Service	.433*	.001	.290*	.025	.435*	.001	.406*	.001	.424*	.001
Employment Status	.380*	.003	.272*	.036	.376*	.003	.371*	.003	.408*	.001
Type of Hospital Facility	.122	.354	.152	.247	.092	.484	.166	.204	.158	.229

Significant at .05 level

Legend:

A - Safe and Quality Practice

G - Quality Improvement

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-
- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|----------------------------|
| B | - | Management of Resources and Environment | H | - | Research |
| C | - | Health Education | I | - | Record Management |
| D | - | Legal Responsibility | J | - | Communication |
| E | - | Ethico-Moral Responsibility | K | - | Collaboration and Teamwork |
| F | - | Personal and Professional Development | | | |

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There are significant relationships that exist between the level of competency of the nurses along specific aspects and the other 4 profile variables namely civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service and employment status.

As to civil status, significant relationship exists with level of competency along quality improvement. The significant positive relationship indicates that as nurses get the chance to have a significant other, the more competent they become on this area.

As to highest educational attainment, positive significant r-values are revealed. This means that higher the level of educational attainment of the nurse, the more competent they are in performing every aspect of their work as nurses. This is also true with number of years in the nursing service and employment status.

PROPOSED DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM FOR NURSES

Rationale: This development program is intended for nurses in the clinical area to enhance their competencies in the different areas of duty.

Safe and quality nursing practice

To conduct regular in-service trainings on updates in the different wards or areas of nursing practice

Participating in design and application of informatics and technology to support decision-making, data management, and information sharing and retrieval

Management of resources and environment

Identifying and alleviating conditions and processes in the healthcare environment that contribute to preventable harm.

Proper waste management system of hospital wastes

Legal Responsibilities

Holding a valid nurse license

Professionalism in nursing practice

Membership in nursing organizations

Quality Improvement

Applying a spirit of inquiry to question processes for best practices, measuring actual practice to compare with desired benchmarks, and implementing appropriate system improvements.

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Participating in design and application of informatics and technology to support decision-making, data management, and information sharing and retrieval

Teamwork and Collaboration

Skilfully connecting, coordinating, and communicating across all disciplines and care team members including the patient and family to assure accurate, timely and effective information sharing, informed decision-making and smooth transitions between providers.

Enhance working relationships to members of the health team

Research

Updating their knowledge and skills through research by pursuing their masteral programs.

Participate in studies which provide outcome measurement like joining the research team of the hospital

Increasing awareness of societal and technological trends, issues and new developments as they apply to nursing

Disseminate research findings to nurses who work directly with the individuals to whom the research applies.

Apply evidence based research in nursing practice

Record Management

Seminar on proper recording and reporting

Document clearly and truthfully what had transpired in the area

Proper safekeeping of records and reports

Communication

Use established communication protocols within the health care agency, and health system.

Proper coordination and collaboration with co-workers

Trainings/ updates on high technology tools of the hospital

Health Education

Assisting clients understand their conditions

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Proper instructions on interventions done to patients

Giving of quality patient care

Involve family members in health care

Personal and Professional Development

Holding myself and others accountable for actions and outcomes.

Assisting client in implementing learning plans such as making a routine health check-ups.

Coaching others in developing their own career plans.

Developing own career plan and measure progress according to plan.

Creating an environment wherein professional and personal growth is an expectation.

Ethico-Moral Responsibility

Conduct seminars on conflict resolutions

Respecting colleagues and other people

Seeking assistance when the need arises

Clear roles and responsibilities

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Chapter 4

Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings of the study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby concluded.

The nurse respondents were young adults, not into marital relationships, Bachelor's degree holder, been in the service for a few years, with regular status and mostly working in public hospitals.

The nurse respondents were most competent in the areas on collaboration and teamwork, legal responsibility, management of resources and environment and personal and professional development.

Nurses who have served for 11 years and above have higher level of competency as compared to those who are 1-3 years in the service. Nurses with regular and contractual status have considered themselves more competent than the nurses who work under job order.

The higher the level of educational attainment, number of years in service, and employment status of the nurse, the more competent they are in performing every aspect of their work as nurses.

The proposed development program is proposed to improve the competencies of nurses.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following are hereby proposed:

Nurses must upgrade their educational qualifications for them to be abreast with the trends in nursing practice thereby enhancing their competencies. Must also attend to seminars to enrich their knowledge and skills.

The respondents must enhance themselves in other core competencies in areas particularly in research,

Nurses regardless of their employment status and length of service must show that they are also competent in all areas of the core competency standards.

Nurses must continue to be abreast with new trends in nursing practice to further enhance their level of competencies in all areas.

The proposed development program can be endorsed for adaption and implementation by the hospitals.

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References

- Afshar, Mohammad, Gandomani, Hamidreza, Alavi, NeginMasoudi 2021 A study on improving nursing clinical competencies in a surgical department: A participatory action research <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/nop2.485>
- Board of Nursing, Core Competency Standards of Nursing Practice, 2012
- Faraji, Azam, MahtabKarimi et al. 2019 Evaluation of clinical competence and its related factors among ICU nurses in Kermanshah-Iran: A cross-sectional study, International Journal of Nursing Science, Published Online
- Ha, Do Thi Ha1, KhanittaNuntaboot, 2020 Factors influencing competency development of nurses as perceived by stakeholders in VietnamBelitung Nursing Journal, 6(4), 103-110
<https://belitungraya.org/BRP/index.php/bnj/index>
- Istomina, Natalia, TarjaSuominen, ArturasRazbadauskas 2011 Competence of Nurses and Factors Associated With It, Medicina Journals Volume 47, Issue 4, <https://www.mdpi.com/1648-9144/47/4/33>
- National Library of Medicine, 2022 Redesigning Continuing Education in the Health Professions, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK219809/>
- National nursing competency Standards, 2012
<https://www.prc.gov.ph/uploaded/documents/Nursing%20Core%20Competency%20Standards%202012.pdf>
- Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, (RA 9173) An Act regulating the practice of Nursing in the Philippines
- Sherwood, Gwen, 2021 Quality and Safety Education for Nurses: Making progress in patient safety, learning from COVID-19, International Journal of Health Sciences <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8169322/>

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Medicine, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20878605/>

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